

RECENT ADVANCES IN FAILURE MECHANICS OF THICK COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are being explored for many new applications, including transportation systems, marine structures, offshore structures, and civil infrastructure. The dimensions of the composite structures being considered, and the stress states which these structures will experience during service, dictate the use of thick composites. In order to design these composite structures with confidence, a knowledge of the deformation and failure of thick composites is essential. Our knowledge in this area is far from complete, and a concerted effort is required to address many of the research issues associated with the use of thick composites subjected to complex three-dimensional states of stress in severe environments. This paper summarizes some of the fundamental research issues in thick composites which are being explored by composites researchers, and provides an overview of some recent accomplishments.

Keywords: Thick composites, failure mechanics, compression failure, hydrostatic pressure.

INTRODUCTION

During the last few decades, composite materials have been used in many aerospace structures to provide enhanced capabilities. This has been possible because of the many attractive properties of polymer matrix composites, which include high specific stiffness and high specific strength. Composite materials are also used in many other fields including sporting goods. Today, researchers are actively involved in exploring the use of composite materials in

transportation systems, energy storage systems, offshore structures, marine structures and civil infrastructure. Some of these newer applications require the use of composites with thicknesses which are greater than those typically used in aerospace applications. With increase of thickness, three-dimensional effects have to be explored and incorporated into models for composite response. The loading which these structures are expected to encounter in service is also different from the loading experienced by most aerospace structures. In particular, significant stress components normal to the surface of the composite structure will occur for many structures under consideration. In underwater or submerged structures, this normal loading is in the form of high hydrostatic pressure.

Thus, there is an increasing interest in establishing a scientific understanding of the response of thick composites to three dimensional loading conditions. This includes studies of deformation, damage initiation, damage growth and failure. This paper describes recent accomplishments in a research program aimed at a fundamental understanding of failure in thick composites subjected to complex loading conditions. During the initial phase of this research, emphasis has been placed on compressive failure in unidirectional and multidirectional composite laminates and in the failure of thick cylindrical shells.

COMPRESSION FAILURE

Failure in thick composites is a very complex phenomenon. A large number of failure modes can occur in composites depending on constituent material properties, microstructure, geometry, loading conditions, and environmental conditions. A major challenge to researchers is the establishment of physically-based quantitative models for the initiation and propagation of damage leading to final failure, accounting for the coupling of failure modes at different scales.

In some of the newer applications of composites, especially in the marine environment, three-dimensional compressive loading states exist. This requires a concerted effort to understand the factors governing compression failure in thick composites. Some recent accomplishments in the compression failure are summarized next.

In an experimental investigation of the different failure mechanisms which can be active during compressive failure of unidirectional fiber composites, Jelf and Fleck [1] identified four mechanisms of failure: fiber failure, elastic microbuckling, matrix failure, and plastic microbuckling. They reviewed theoretical models for the prediction of the onset of these failure mechanisms and used experimental data for the validation of the models. Plastic microbuckling was identified to be the dominant failure mechanism in polymer matrix composites; for this failure mode compressive strength is dictated by the shear yield strength of the matrix and the misalignment of the fibers. They established a failure map for carbon fiber-PEEK and carbon fiber-epoxy composites, showing which failure mode is predicted for given values of in-plane composite elastic shear modulus G_c and ratio of pure shear yield stress to initial fiber misalignment. The failure loci of several different polymer matrix composites were plotted in this failure map, and all of these were shown to fall in the domain in which plastic microbuckling is the dominant failure mechanism.

Budiansky and Fleck [2] established models for microbuckling in a unidirectional composite

subjected to combined axial compression and in-plane shear, including the effects of matrix yielding and initial imperfections in the form of fiber misalignment. The strength of unidirectional carbon fiber-epoxy laminates in combined axial compression and shear was measured by Jelf and Fleck [3] using composite tubes in combined compression and torsion. These experimental results support the predictions of Budiansky and Fleck and suggest an average fiber misalignment of 2 to 3 degrees.

Failure mechanisms and failure progression in thick composite laminates under compressive loading were investigated by Daniel, et al [4]. These studies of unidirectional and cross-ply laminates of AS4/3501-6 and IM6G/3501-6 composite materials have shown that, with increasing load, the weakest fibers, or the fibers which have the least lateral support fail first. For the carbon/epoxy materials tested, failure took the form of kinking, since the 3501-6 matrix is relatively stiff and brittle. Kink bands were not confined to one plane.

The effect of holes and cutouts on compression failure of carbon fiber/epoxy (T800/924C) multidirectional laminates was studied by Soutis et al [5]. In investigations of a laminate with a stacking sequence of $[(+45/-45/0_2)_2]$, with a circular hole, the authors showed that the dominant failure mechanism is fiber microbuckling in the zero degree plies surrounded by delaminations. The buckle zone initiates at the edges of the hole at 80-85% of the failure load and grows stably under increasing applied load for approximately 2 mm. Then unstable growth begins and catastrophic failure occurs.

Sun and Jun [6] have used numerical methods for the study of fiber microbuckling in unidirectional fiber composites including nonlinear behavior of matrix and fiber misalignment. The bifurcation buckling criterion required utilizing the concept of incremental deformation with initial stress. The analysis showed reasonable correlation with available AS4/3501-6 composite compression test data.

In a theoretical investigation by Weitsman and Chung [7], compression failure in unidirectional composites was explored, including the combined effects of matrix material nonlinear behavior and geometric imperfections in the form of initial fiber waviness and random fiber spacing. The latter type of geometric imperfection, with probability distribution guided by physical aspects, introduces imbalances in the support provided by the matrix against fiber buckling, resulting in highly localized transverse loads on the fibers. These transverse loads could lead to fiber micro-kinking and bring about a transition from failure through micro-buckling to collapse by micro-kinking.

FAILURE OF CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

In addition to studies of the response of flat rectangular composite laminates, thick composite cylindrical shells subjected to a variety of loads including axial compression, external hydrostatic pressure, internal hydrostatic pressure, and combinations of these stress states have been investigated by several researchers.

A series of experiments were conducted by Garala [8] on graphite fiber reinforced composite cylinders subjected to bi-axial compressive loading. These experiments on cylinders with internal diameters of 4 and 8 inches, have shown that premature failures can occur due to a

variety of processing defects, including fiber waviness. The complex failure process involves a coupling of failure modes, including fiber microbuckling, kink bands and delaminations.

The buckling of thick composite cylindrical shells under external pressure was investigated by Kardomateas [9]. Using a formulation based on three-dimensional theory of elasticity, a solution was obtained. This solution showed that the classical shell theory predictions can produce highly non-conservative results on the critical load of composite shells with moderately thick construction.

In studies of the buckling of ring stiffened thick composite cylindrical shells, Sridharan [10] has identified two distinctive modes of buckling. The first mode is the short-wave local buckling, in which buckling occurs between the stiffeners with several half-waves in the circumferential direction; the nodes of buckling waves in the longitudinal direction coincide with the location of the stiffeners. The second is the long-wave overall buckling in which the stiffeners suffer radial displacements together with the shell. The buckling mode consists of a small number in the circumferential direction. Interactive effects between these modes were determined. Imperfection sensitivity under coincident buckling was examined for a variety of specially orthotropic and anisotropic layered shells. It was demonstrated that modal interaction can typically cause a reduction of 40% of the critical load for imperfections of such magnitude as may be unavoidable in practice.

Dvorak and Prochazka [11] have investigated a thick-walled composite cylinder consisting of many different cylindrically orthotropic layers, loaded by uniform, axisymmetric surface tractions and by piecewise uniform eigenstrains in the layers. Utilizing recent innovative methods for the analysis of transformation fields [12,13], they established a theoretical framework for the evaluation of internal strain and stress fields with mechanical and transformation influence functions. They also provided an optimization procedure for the identification of eigenstrain distributions that adjust the stresses in the layers to certain prescribed levels. For a thick composite cylindrical shell subjected to external hydrostatic pressure, an active internal steel liner was shown to significantly reduce the internal stress fields in the composite cylinder, thereby reducing the potential for premature failure.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, some important research issues relevant to thick composites were discussed, and selected recent accomplishments were summarized. To permit design engineers to use thick composites in critical structures with confidence, major advances are necessary in our understanding of the behavior of these materials under complex states of stress. Continuing research is needed in many areas, including: the coupling of failure modes in multiaxial composite laminates and cylindrical shells; interaction between material and structural instability; nature of progression of damage; effect of defects; dynamic response and dynamic failure; environmental effects; and quantitative nondestructive evaluation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research reported here was primarily supported by the Solid Mechanics Program of the Office of Naval Research.

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